

On a scale of 1 to 6, on which 1 is complete rejection and 6 complete approval:

Please state in how far you reject or approve following statements:	I reject fully	I reject	I reject slightly	I approve slightly	I approve	I approve fully
I am not often in nature.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like experiencing and discovering nature and my surrounding.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to observe and identify animals and plants.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am mainly outside because I have to be.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to meet people in nature or visit events.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I have many memories with the landscape here.	1	2	3	4	5	6
In nature I can relax and recover.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to move outside and do sports.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to be outside even when the weather is bad.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to work outside and make my hands dirty.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I think nature is beautiful.	1	2	3	4	5	6

How important is it for you, that the following will remain part of the agricultural land?	Very important	Rather important	Rather unimportant	Not important
Bees and bumblebees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wolfs and bears	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herbs in arable land	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Trees, Hedges and bushes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

On a scale from 1 to 6, on which 1 is complete rejection and 6 is complete approval:

Please state in how far you reject or approve following statements:	I reject fully	I reject	I reject slightly	I approve slightly	I approve	I approve fully
Humans worry too much about the destruction of nature.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Using nature as resource for industry and economy is more important than nature conservation.	1	2	3	4	5	6
We have to take responsibility for the global consequences of our behavior.	1	2	3	4	5	6
We humans have the right to use nature as we like.	1	2	3	4	5	6
It is important to me, that children are introduced to nature.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Natur is strong enough, we don't have to protect it from human influence.	1	2	3	4	5	6

The destruction of nature in our country frightens me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
All Animals and plants have a right to live.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I think nature conservation in our country is not important.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I fear that for our children and grand-children there won't be much unimpaired nature left.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am angry about that humans treat nature so carefree.	1	2	3	4	5	6

	Always	Very often	Sometimes	Very rarely	Never
How often do you use wood as a source of fire?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
How often do you fetch fresh water from a natural fountain?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
How often do you take materials out of nature for decoration and arts?	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	All year	A few month a year	Never
Do you grown your own fruits or vegetables ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Very important	Rather important	Rather unimportant	Not important
In how far is it important for you that your food comes from your own region?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
And how is this with clothes? How important is that your clothes originate in this country?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

On a scale from 1 to 6, on which 1 is complete rejection and 6 is complete approval:

Please state in how far you reject or approve following statements:	I reject fully	I reject	I reject slightly	I approve slightly	I approve	I approve fully
I can easily live without nature.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I feel connected to all living things on earth.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I think a lot about how much animals have to suffer because of humans.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Even if I am in a big city, I notice the nature around me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
The thought to be in a forest far from any civilization frightens me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Nature helps me to feel home.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am not separate from nature, but a part of it.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am very aware of environmental issues.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I think a lot about how my behavior affects the environment.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Some animals are destined to get extinct eventually.	1	2	3	4	5	6

In nature I have the feeling there exists something mightier than me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Our landscape is a big part of our culture.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Humans are dependent on intact and healthy nature	1	2	3	4	5	6
Following pictures show managed nature. Please indicate if the pictures show 1 – ‘This is definitely not nature for me’ to 6 – ‘that is definitely nature for me’						
A	1	2	3	4	5	6
B	1	2	3	4	5	6
C	1	2	3	4	5	6
D	1	2	3	4	5	6
E	1	2	3	4	5	6
F	1	2	3	4	5	6

Are you a member of an organization/ club that is concerned with nature?

Yes

Aktive

No

Passive

Since which year do you live here?

Have you lived before that in this region?

Yes

No

If yes, since when?: _____

Are there children under 12 years living in your household?

Yes

No

Please state your year of birth: ____

Which nationality do you have? Which ethnic group do you belong to?: _____

Is one of your parents not been born in Romania/Germany?

Yes

No

If yes, in which country? _____

What is the highest general school education degree you have?

Answer categories adjusted to the country in question

Which occupational degree do you have? You can state multiple degrees.
Answer categories adjusted to the country in question